

RTD symptom development in plants infected at different stages in the field. Bali, Indonesia, 1989 dry season.

Stage at inoculation	Plants tested (no.)	Plants infected (no.)	Mean duration ^d (d)				
			Incubation ^b	Gr. 1-Gr. 2	Gr. 2-Gr. 3	Gr. 3-Gr. 4	Gr. 4-Gr. 5
1 DBT	28	14	11.28 b	1.14 c	9.71 d	7.85 a	2.92 a
1 WT	27	13	8.92 a	0.00 a	3.30 bc	7.38 a	14.91 c
2 WT	27	16	9.18 a	0.25 ab	2.93 b	13.37 b	6.12 b
3 WT	27	8	11.12 b	0.37 b	1.50 a	13.37 b	6.87 b
5 WT	27	11	14.54 c	0.27 ab	4.72 c	-	-
7 WT	27	8	18.37 d	1.62 d	-	-	-

^a In a column means followed by the same letter are not significant different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^b Incubation = from infection to Gr. 1.; Gr. 1, <50% of a leaf discolored; Gr. 2, >50% of a leaf discolored; Gr. 4, all discolored leaves dry but still attached; Gr. 5, leaves stunted but not yellow or dry.

observation was terminated. Plants infected at 7 WT did not develop Gr. 3 symptoms. Distinct changes in leaf color did not occur, but panicle development was affected in plants infected at 9 WT.

RTD-infected plants in fields develop symptoms different from those in the laboratory. Many of the hills infected at early stages are overlooked if leaf yellowing is the basis for diagnosis. We confirmed that this holds for many susceptible varieties, such as IR36 and IR64. □

Integrated pest management—insects

Damage by rice thrips and defoliators in southern Bhutan

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We sampled modern rice varieties (MVs) BR153, Jaya, and BW293-2 and traditional varieties (TVs) Atti, Dhursray, and Mashino bhog for rice thrip damage during Aug 1989 in 11 fields in Gaylephug, Bhutan. Crop age was 26-60 d after transplanting (DT). We recorded damaged leaves from three replications of 20 randomly selected hills per field.

Seven fields in four villages were sampled for damage by defoliators. Rice varieties were the same except for

Table 1. Damage to rice leaves due to feeding of *Haplothrips* sp. Gaylephug, Bhutan, August 1989.

Location	Variety	Crop age ^a (DT)	Damaged leaves ^b (% ± SE)
Lodrai	Modern	26	26.9 ± 0.3
Lodrai	Traditional	26	3.5 ± 0.1
Bhur Farm	Modern	33	13.2 ± 2.2
Bhur Farm	Modern	33	20.8 ± 1.3
Bhur Farm	Traditional	33	1.5 ± 0.5
Sumitar	Modern	35	9.0 ± 2.5
Panpani	Modern	45	10.8 ± 1.3
Bhur Farm	Modern	47	7.2 ± 0.3
Bhur Farm	Modern	47	7.2 ± 0.6
Bhur Farm	Traditional	47	1.8 ± 0.5
Surey	Traditional	60	4.7 ± 1.3

^a Days after transplanting. ^b Based on 20 randomly selected hills/field. Av of 3 replications.

$$\text{Damaged leaves (\%)} = \frac{\text{damaged leaves}}{\text{total leaves}} \times 100.$$

BW2Y3-2. Crop age was 45-60 DT.

Thrip damage was 7.2-26.9% in the MVs and 1.5-4.7% in the TVs (Table 1). Defoliator damage was 0.8-6.6% in the MVs and 0.4-5.8% in the TVs (Table 2).

The MV selections appear to be more susceptible to thrips than TVs in southern Bhutan. Defoliators, however, showed no distinct preference. □

Effect of foliar spray insecticides on brown planthopper (BPH) resurgence in rice

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Effect of foliar spray insecticides on BPH population. ^a Farmer's field, Banglana, Nakornpatom Provis. Central Thailand, 1990 wet season.

Insecticide ^b	Rate (g active ingredient/ha)	BPH population (no./8 m ²) ^a			Resurgence ratio (67 DAS)	Yield (t/ha)
		17 DAS	52 DAS	67 DAS		
ns						
Alphacypermethrin + BPMC 41% EC	410	6.75	12.25 cd	770 c	0.142	4.5 ab
Alphacypermethrin + BPMC 41 % EC	820	8.75	8.25 d	487 c	0.089	4.6 a
Methyl parathion 50% EC	250	5.75	24 bc	8260 a	1.525	4.5 ab
BPMC 50% EC	300	7	13.5 cd	567 c	0.104	4.2 ab
Buprofezin + decamethrin 5.625% EC	56.25	8.75	13.5 cd	315 c	0.058	4.7 a
Cypermethrin 25% EC	25	6.5	40 a	2504 c	0.462	4.0 b
Monocrotophos 60% WSC	300	6.25	10 cd	415 c	0.076	4.8 a
Decamethrin 3% EC	7.5	10.5	37 ab	8104 a	1.496	4.0 b
Control		9	18 cd	5416 ab	-	4.4 ab

^a In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT. ^b EC = emulsifiable concentrate, WSC = water-soluble concentrate. ^c Average of four replications.

Table 2. Damage to rice leaves by defoliators^a in Gaylephug, Bhutan, August 1989.

Location	Variety	Crop age (DT)	Damaged leaves (% ± SE)
Bhur Farm	Modern	47	6.4 ± 0.84
Bhur Farm	Modern	47	6.6 ± 1.04
Bhur Farm	Traditional	47	5.8 ± 0.61
Panpani	Modern	45	0.8 ± 0.20
Patabari	Modern	60	5.4 ± 0.56
Patabari	Traditional	60	1.2 ± 0.60
Surey	Traditional	60	0.4 ± 0.10

^a Rice leaffolders *Morasmia* and *Cnaphalocrocis*, case worm *Nymphula*, and an unidentified larva

$$\text{Damaged leaves (\%)} = \frac{\text{damage leaves}}{\text{total leaves}} \times 100$$

We conducted a trial in a farmer's field in Banglana, Central Thailand, during 1990 wet season to determine the effects of foliar sprays on BPH. Plots of 12 × 15 m² were laid out in a randomized complete block design and direct seeded using susceptible variety Suphan 60. Nine insecticide treatments were applied at 20, 35, 45, and 60 d after sowing (DAS) using 500 liters water/ha with a motor-

ized knapsack mistblower. We used a D-vac suction sampler to assess insect populations in 8 m² of each plot.

BPH populations in plots sprayed with methyl parathion and decamethrin were higher than in control plots. Plots

treated with monocrotophos yielded the most, followed by plots with al-phacypermethrin + BPMC (see table). Plots treated with cypermethrin and decamethrin yielded less than the control plots.

The results imply that methyl parathion and decamethrin could induce high BPH densities. Treated fields did not yield higher than the control, which suggests that insecticide applications might not benefit yields. □

Hourly catches of yellow stem borer (YSB)

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YSB moth catches were recorded from 6 p.m. to 6 a.m. at the Rice Research Station, Tirur, for a 24-d period coinciding with peak brood emergence. Three traps—a local bamboo light trap with 40 W incandescent bulb, and modified Robinson light traps with 125 W mercury vapor lamp and 200 W incandescent bulb—were located 100 m apart. Moth catches were transferred to separate containers at hourly intervals, separated by sex, counted, and a cumulative percentage worked out (see figure).

Cumulative percentage of YSB catch in light traps at hourly intervals from 6 p.m. to 6 a.m.

Peak moth catch occurred at 9 to 10 p.m. Sixty-four percent of the females and 62% of the males were caught before

midnight. There was a slight spurt in moth activity from 1 to 4 a.m. for females and from 4 to 5 a.m. for males. □

Effect of rice stage and GLH density on pipunculid parasitism on green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* in Bali, Indonesia

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Pipunculid flies are natural enemies of GLH, a vector of rice tungro, but their activities in the tropics are not well known. Observations in major rice-producing areas of Sumatra, Java, Kalimantan, Sulawesi, Bali, and Lombok from 1986 to 1990 showed cases in which pipunculid parasitism rate was more than 80%.

We surveyed 83 ricefields in asynchronously planted areas in Bali for this

Pipunculid parasitism on *N. virescens* in 1989 dry season and 1989/90 wet season.^a

Rice crop age	Dry season			Wet season		
	GLH caught (no.)	GLH parasitized (%)	MF (%)	GLH caught (no.)	GLH parasitized (%)	MF (%)
Nursery beds	63	6.3	43.6	84	7.1	62.0
3-4 WT	76	14.5	41.4	186	14.5	56.6
5-6 WT	151	10.6	21.1	738	21.8	16.0
7-8 WT	200	23.5	1.4	148	29.1	5.5
9-10 WT	-	-	-	203	26.1	8.6
Ratoon	105	6.7	47.8	64	28.1	14.3

^aWT = weeks after transplanting. MF = proportion of mature females among parasite-free females.

study. GLH adults were collected by net sweeps in 1989 dry season and 1989/90 wet season. Insects were dissected under a binocular microscope to observe for pipunculid larvae and for the proportion of mature females among parasite-free females.

Relation of pipunculid parasitism rate to GLH adult density in ricefields 5-8 WT. Regression line is $Y = 17.5 + 10.5X$. $r = 0.49$ (<0.01), where Y is are sin-transformed.